

Effects of Electronic Auditory Personal Gadgets on Hearing among Medical StudentsShruthi HS¹, Shilpa R², Nisha K¹¹Assistant Professor, Department of ENT, Sri Siddhartha Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, T. Begur, Nelamangala, Bengaluru Rural 562123²Associate Professor, Department of ENT, Sri Siddhartha Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, T. Begur, Nelamangala, Bengaluru Rural 562123³Senior Resident, Department of ENT, Sri Siddhartha Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, T. Begur, Nelamangala, Bengaluru Rural 562123

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Shruthi HS

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** After the COVID-19 pandemic, usage of electronic auditory gadgets has increased exponentially for academic and recreational purposes among the medical students which impairs hearing. Hence it is important to create awareness among them about these gadgets.**Aim of the Study:** To evaluate the loss of hearing in medical students by subjective and objective assessment methods and correlating the degree of hearing loss with the nature of electronic gadgets used by them.**Materials:** 132 Students of all phases were given a subjective questionnaire which had details of gadget usage and symptoms related to the loss of hearing. Pure tone audiometry was done in all. Association of degree of hearing loss with type of gadgets used, duration of usage and related symptoms were documented and analysed.**Results:** There were 84 female (63.6%) students and, 48 male students (36.4%). The mean age of the participants was 21.15±2.50 years. The primary purpose for using hearing gadgets was for education 81(61.3%). Ear Pods were used in 67(50.8%) and was the most popular type of hearing gadget, followed by earphones 34(25.8%) and headphones in 19(14.4%). 54 (40.9%) of them had used the gadget for more than three years. The most common symptom was itching sensation in the ears in 41(31.1%) followed by burning sensation in the ear 40(30.3%). Tinnitus complained by 32(24.2%) and pain in the ear by 19(14.4%). Only 39(29.5%) participants have experienced decreased hearing.**Conclusion:** In the study, the type of gadgets used, duration of usage of gadgets in years and usage hours per day had no significant association with hearing loss. Hearing loss was detected more at 8000 and 4000Hz indicating noise induced hearing loss. Auditory gadgets should be used cautiously by students as it damages their hearing which further has deterrent effects on their learning and communication.**Keywords:** Noise Induced Hearing Loss, Auditory Gadgets, Ear Phones, Ear Pods, Pure Tone Audiometry (PTA).

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Noise induced hearing loss (NIHL) is a preventable type of hearing loss. Recently usage of headphone and earphone has increased among the general population. Hearing capabilities in medical students is essential in their daily learning as well as in communication with the patients and peers. Defective hearing abilities lead to poor communication and learning skills. [2] After the COVID-19 pandemic usage of Electronic auditory gadgets has increased exponentially for both academic and recreational purpose among medical students. These devices have potential of generating sounds above 85Db. [3, 4] Noise induced hearing loss

(NIHL) is a medical condition developed in individuals with normal hearing following exposure to high intensity noise. NIHL is bilateral, irreversible and the hearing loss is sensorineural type. The risk of NIHL due to long periods of exposure to noise is present in 14% of the total world population. [5] Originally NIHL was described in occupational noise producing workplaces and WHO has estimated that the NIHL was 33% of all cases of hearing-impaired diseases. The primary impact of NIHL in a person is impaired communication, leading to strained relations with the members of the family, colleagues and fellow students and disharmony in the workplace. [6] If NIHL is not treated especially

in adults, leads to indirect effects on the health, psychosocial, and economic aspects further leading to social isolation and reduced quality of life (QoL). [7] And in adults leads to lower job performance those results in individual income losses. The prevalence of NHIL is increasing every year as per latest published literature and about 40% of them belong to the age group of 16 and 25 years. [8,] In Southeast Asia the prevalence of hearing loss is from 04.6% to 08.8%. The burden of hearing impairment in India is also substantially high at 09.14%. [10, 11 and 12] WHO in their resolution of WHA70.13 has asked the Government of all countries to combine ear and hearing care into their national health system frame work? [13] It has introduced apps like “Hear WHO” and other technology-based solutions enable screening for ear diseases and hearing loss to be undertaken in settings with limited training and resources. [14] Most of the medical colleges during the COVID-19 period conducted online classes for completing their teaching schedules which has further increased the utilization of AEI. [14] The literature on the burden of hearing impairment among the students of medical Colleges in India and using smart phone based screening assessments is also not available. In this context the present study was conducted to evaluate the loss of hearing in medical students by subjective and objective assessment methods and correlating the degree of hearing loss with the nature of electronic gadgets used by them.

Materials and Methods

Place of Study: Department of ENT, Sri Siddhartha Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, T. Begur, Nelamangala, Bengaluru Rural 562123

Study Type: Observational study

Study Period: March 2024– May 2024 (3 months)

Primary Source of Data: The undergraduate medical students of all phases of both genders between the age group of 18-25.

Sample Size: Sample size is calculated using the formula sample size estimation for proportion

$$N = \frac{z^2 \cdot p \cdot (1-p)}{d^2}$$

Where: n: sample size, z: standard normal table value for given level of significance p: prevalence rate α : precision;

n= 132

Reason: Prevalence rate in the previous study is 9.5

Sampling Method: Convenient sampling

Inclusion Criteria: Medical students of all phases willing to join the study were included.

Exclusion Criteria: Medical students with history of ear trauma, ear discharge and decreased hearing were excluded. Medical students who have undergone ear surgeries were excluded. Medical students with family history of decreased hearing were excluded. Medical students with history of ototoxic drugs usage were excluded.

Method of collection of data: Institutional ethical committee clearance was taken and permission was taken from principal to conduct study on students. The medical students of all phases were thoroughly explained regarding nature and purpose of study and invited to take part in the study. Informed written consent were taken from students who agreed. The medical students were provided with a pre-designed and pre-tested structured questionnaire which includes socio-demographic details and other details related to usage of gadgets and symptoms of hearing loss. (Table 1)

Table1: Questionnaire

Student Number	Age:	Gender:	MBBS Phase	Contact Number:
1.	Are you using electronic auditory personal gadgets? a) YES b) NO			
2.	Purpose of usage: a) educational purpose b) Relaxation c) gaming d) others			
3.	Which type of gadget? a) Earphone b) headphone c) air pods d) others			
4.	From how long the usage is? a) 1 year b) 2 years c) 3 years d) more than 3 years			
5.	How many hours in a day? a) 30 mins. b) 1 to 2 hours c) 2-3 hours d) more than 3 hours			
6.	Preferred listening volume? a) High volume b) medium volume c) low volume			
7.	Preferred type of music? a) Melody b) rock c) others			
8.	Do you have any of the following symptoms during or after usage? a) Ear pain b) burning sensation c) itching in the ear d) ringing sensation			
9.	Have you noticed decreased hearing since the usage? a) YES b) NO			
10.	Do you ask people to repeat the words during the conversations? a) YES b) NO			
11.	Is there any family history of hearing loss? a) YES b) NO			
12.	Is there any previous history of ear discharge? a) YES b) NO			
13.	Have you undergone ear surgery before? a) YES b) NO			
14.	Are you using any medications since long time? a) YES b) NO			
15.	Do you have any history of trauma to the ear? a) YES b) NO			

Personal details: Student number: Age: Sex: MBBS phase:

Contact details: After the collection of filled questionnaire, the responses to them were analyzed. Then the study subjects were selected based on inclusion and exclusion criteria and were called to the ENT OPD. Detailed history was taken regarding usage of auditory gadgets and ear symptoms and ENT examination was done. Audiological evaluation was done by pure tone audiometry. Both Air conduction and bone conduction thresholds were identified at frequencies from 250 Hz to 8000 Hz and audiogram results were graded.

Results

In the study, there are 132 participants. All the data were collected and entered to a Microsoft excel sheet and analysed using Jamovi 2.5.6 software. There were 84(63.6%) female students and 48 (36.4%) male students. The mean age of participants was 21±0.97 years. The primary reason for using hearing gadgets was for education in 81(61.3%), students followed by for relaxation in 29(22%) students. A significant number of participants used them for both education and relaxation in 22(16.7%). Ear Pods 67(50.8%) was the most popular type of hearing gadgets used in the study followed by earphones in 34(25.8%) students and headphones in 19(14.4%) students. A combination of gadgets was used by a smaller

percentage of participants in 12(9%) students. A majority of participants have been using hearing gadgets for over three years in 54 (40.9%) students indicating a long- term usage followed by 02 years in 42(31.8%) students, 01year in 26(19.7%) students and 3years in 10(7.6%) students. A significant portion of participants used their gadgets for 1-2 hours per day i.e. in 72 (54.6%) students with a smaller percentage of them using the gadgets for longer durations like 2-3 hours in 25(18.9%) students and more than 3 hours in 25(18.9%) students. very few students used the gadgets for 30 min to 1 hour i.e. in 10 (7.6%) students.

The majority of participants i.e. 90 (68.2%) students preferred medium volume levels, while a smaller percentage preferred high 15(11.4%)and 27(20.4%) students preferred low volumes. Participants had varied music preferences, with melody liked by 55(41.7%) students and it was the most popular option followed by rock music by 46(34.8%) students. Combination music was preferred by 31(23.5%) students. The most common symptoms reported were itching sensation in 41(31.1%) students followed by burning sensation in 40(30.3%) students, ringing sensation in 32(24.2%) students and earpain19(14.4%) students. 39(29.5%) participants had experienced decreased hearing, and the majority i.e. 93(70.5%) students never experienced loss of hearing. (Table 2)

Table2: Socio-demographic details and gadget usage pattern and symptoms

Study characteristics	n=132		
Gender	n(%)	Duration of Usage per day	n(%)
Male	48 (36.4)	30min-1 Hour	10 (7.6)
Female	84 (63.6)	1-2 Hours	72 (54.6)
		2-3 Hours	25 (18.9)
Age (Mean± S.D)	21±0.97	>3 Hours	25 (18.9)
Purpose of using hearing gadgets		Preferred volume	
Education	81 (61.3)	High	15 (11.4)
Relaxation	29 (22.0)	Medium	90 (68.2)
Both	22 (16.7)	Low	27 (20.4)
Type of gadgets used		Preferred type of music	
Ear Pods	67 (50.8)	Melody	55 (41.7)
Earphones	34 (25.8)	Rock	46 (34.8)
Headphones	19 (14.4)	Combination	31 (23.5)
Combination of gadgets	12 (9.0)		
Duration of Usage Since		Symptoms (if any)	
1 Year	26 (19.7)	Ear pain	19 (14.4)
2 Years	42 (31.8)	Burning sensation	40 (30.3)
3 Years	10 (7.6)	Itching	41 (31.1)
>3 Years	54 (40.9)	Ringing sensation	32 (24.2)
--		Complaints of decreased hearing	
		Yes	39 (29.5)
		No	93 (70.5)

The statistical tests chi-square test& fisher exact test was used to analyses the relationship between

the study variables and hearing loss.

67(48.4%) i.e. majority of the students had minimal

hearing loss. 10 (07.57%) students had mild hearing loss, 07(05.30%) students had moderate hearing loss and 01 (0.75%) student had moderately severe hearing loss. Hearing loss was more in the right ear compared to the left ear. Hearing loss was detected more at 8000Hz followed by 4000Hz frequencies. Hearing loss among the males was 35.4%, and among females it was 33.3%. There was no significant association between gender and hearing loss (p-value = 0.808). There was a weak association between the purpose of using hearing gadgets and hearing loss (p-value=0.126). While the data suggests that those using hearing gadgets for education might be slightly more likely to experience hearing loss, this association is not statistically significant. There is no significant association between the type of gadgets used and hearing loss (p-value = 0.704). This indicates that the type of hearing gadget (Ear Pods, earphones, headphones, or a combination) does not appear to influence the likelihood of experiencing hearing loss.

There was no significant association between the duration of hearing gadget usage and hearing loss per se (p-values 0.44). There was no significant association between the duration of daily hearing gadget usage and hearing loss (p-values of 0.716).

This indicates that the amount of time spent using hearing gadgets each day does not appear to be a factor in determining whether someone experiences hearing loss. There was no significant association between preferred volume level and hearing loss (p-value = 0.788). There was no significant association between the preferred type of music (melody, rock, or combination) and hearing loss (p-values of 0.825). There was a significant association between complaints of decreased hearing and actual hearing loss (Fisher's exact test statistic, p-value < 0.001). This confirms that individuals who report decreased hearing are indeed more likely to have hearing loss. (Table 3)

Table3: Audiometry test outcome of the participants in the study

Frequency	Ear	Normal n (%)	Minimal n (%)	Mild n (%)	Moderate n (%)	Moderately n (%)	Severe	Mean± SD
250 Hz	Right	113(85.6)	19(14.4)	-	-	-		11.70 ± 4.57
	Left	120(91)	11(08.3)	1(0.8)	-	-		12.42 ± 3.97
500 Hz	Right	111(84)	20(15.2)	1(0.8)	-	-		13.60 ± 4.79
	Left	115(87)	15(11.4)	2(1.5)	-	-		13.37 ± 4.56
1000 Hz	Right	109(82)	22(16.7)	-	01(0.8)	-		13.90 ± 5.03
	Left	114(86)	16(12.1)	1(0.8)	01(0.8)	-		13.71 ± 4.69
2000 Hz	Right	111(84)	20(15.2)	-	01(0.8)	-		13.83 ± 5.16
	Left	109(82)	22(16.7)	-	01(0.8)	-		13.83 ± 5.23
4000 Hz	Right	110(83)	20(15.2)	01(0.8)	01(0.8)	-		13.94 ± 5.56
	Left	111(84)	20(15.2)	-	01(0.8)	-		13.64 ± 5.49
8000 Hz	Right	107(81)	21(15.9)	03(2.3)	01(0.8)	-		14.66 ± 6.36
	Left	106(80)	24(18.2)	01(0.8)	-	01(0.8)		14.24 ± 6.16
Hearing loss based on Audiometry test						Final D Diagnosis		
Frequency	Right ear n (%)		Left ear n (%)		-	Hearing Loss		n (%)
250 Hz	19 (14.4)		12 (9.1)			Present	87(65.9)	
500 Hz	21 (15.9)		17 (12.9)			Absent	45(34.9)	
1000 Hz	23 (17.4)		18 (13.6)					
2000 Hz	21 (15.9)		23 (17.4)					
4000 Hz	22 (16.7)		21 (15.9)					
8000 Hz	25 (18.9)		26 (19.7)					

The proportions of the hearing loss in the participants based on the different variables used in the study were shown in the Fig 1.

Figure 1: Proportions of hearing loss in the study variables among the study participants

The proportion of Hearing loss in the study variables among the subjects was shown in the graph in Fig 1.

Discussion

In the present study, there were 84(63.6%) female students and 48 (36.4%) male students. The mean age of participants was 21±0.97 years. Majority of participants were females in a similar study by similar to Asgar et al [2]. The mean age observed in the present study was very similar to Thomas et al [5] and sharma et al [3]. In this study auditory gadgets were used primarily for education in 81

(61.3%), students followed by for relaxation in 29 (22%) students, for both education and relaxation in 22(16.7%). Mohammad et al [4] from their study reported the Purpose of usage was educational in 61% and majority from the remaining used for music, but the study was conducted in non-medical general students. Ear pods was most commonly used in this study similar to this by Asghar et al [2] whereas earphones were used by majority in the study by syam et al, [7] Asgar et al [2] and rekha et al [6]. In the present study 90 (68.2%) students preferred medium volume levels similar to study by Rekha et al [6] whereas in a study by sharma et al

[3] high volume was preferred. Ringing sensation was reported by 32(24.2%) students in this study. In a similar study by Syam et al [7] ringing sensation was found in 32% of the subjects. In this study duration of usage of gadgets in years and hours of usage per day had no significant association; the p values were 0.44 and 0.716 respectively. But in the study by Sharma et al [3] there was a significant association between the duration of usage of gadgets and also the hours of usage in a single day. [3] In our study hearing loss was more in right ear compared to left ear similar to asgar et al [2], Thomas et al [5] and Sharma et al [3] and there was no significant association with type of music and hearing loss similar to Sharma et al study. [3] In this study hearing loss were detected more at 8000 and 4000Hz whereas in study by Asgar et al [2] and Thomas et al [5], sensorineural hearing loss was reported more in lower frequencies of 250Hz and 500Hz. There was a significant association between complaints of decreased hearing and actual hearing loss (Fisher's exact test statistic, p-value < 0.001) in this study. This confirms that individuals who report decreased hearing are indeed more likely to have hearing loss. (Table 3) Asgar et al [2] reported identical findings as found in our study. Noise induced hearing loss comes under sensorineural hearing loss which presents as a bilateral progressive loss which once established is irreversible only partly manageable though totally preventable. In some cases hearing aids or cochlear implants may be required. In early stages steroids can be used to recover loss of hearing in the patients. From the literature, it is clearly evident that exposure to high-level music produces several physiological changes in the auditory system that leads to a variety of perceptual effects. Damage to the outer hair cells within the cochlea leads to a loss of sensitivity to weak sounds, loudness recruitment (a more rapid than normal growth of loudness with increasing sound level), and reduced frequency selectivity. Damage to inner hair cells and/or synapses leads to degeneration of neurons in the auditory nerve and to a reduced flow of information to the brain. This leads to poorer auditory discrimination and may contribute to a reduced sensitivity to the temporal fine structure of sounds and to poor pitch perception. Exposure to noise between 90 and 140 db damages the cochlea metabolically. Larger the number of decibels and higher the volume used using AEs, the more would be the hearing loss. Noise induced hearing loss is seen more in occupational settings but because of increased usage it is occurring in general population also. The shift from physical teaching and learning methods used earlier to online teaching during and after the pandemic further increased the chances of hearing loss in students. Strategies towards improving student awareness and attitudes against the use of auditory gadgets are required. There is urgent need to take

Earphone volume alerts seriously.

Conclusion

Auditory gadgets should be used cautiously by students as it damages their hearing which further has deterrent effects on their learning and communication.

Limitations of study: Limitations of our study are sample size is less compared to other studies.

Acknowledgements: We take this opportunity to thank the principal of SSIMS& RC forgiving us the permission to conduct this study. A special thanks to all the students of all the batches who participated in this study. Our sincere thanks to Ms Chaithra, audiologist, Dept. of ENT and Ms. Dhanusha, statistician, Dept. of community medicine for their tireless contribution to the study.

References

1. Mogan K A, Tiwari P, Joseph B, Katia A, Kumar A Chugh A.A Smartphone based assessment of hearing impairment among students of a medical college, Delhi, A cross-sectional study. *Indian J Community Med.* 2023; 48:196-200.
2. Asgar S, Khan H, Parveen S, Rafi SMT. Frequency of hearing loss among medical students using electroacoustic device. *Pak J Med Sci.* 2022;38(3):668- 673
3. Sharma Y, Mishra G, Mahida DA. Effect on Hearing due to Amplified Music Exposure. *Int J Otorhinolaryngol clin* 2022;14(1):22-25
4. Mohammad Poorasl A, Hajizadeh M, Marin S, Heydari P, Ghalenoei M. Prevalence and Pattern of Using Headphones and Its Relationship with Hearing Loss among Students. *Health Scope.* 2019;8 (1):e65901. <https://doi.org/10.5812/jhealthscope.65901>.
5. Thomas CA, E Benezzer R, Joice YS. Prevalence of sensorineural hearing loss among medical students who are chronic mobile phone and earphone users in Trivandrum, south Kerala, India. *Indian J Forensic community Med* 2019;6(2):81- 85.
6. Rekha T, Unnikrishnan B, Mithra PP, Kumar N, Bukelo MJ, Ballala k. Perceptions and practices regarding use of personal listening devices among medical students in coastal south India. *Noise Health* 2011;13:329-332.
7. Syam Sasidharan, Sheetal Rai, Gangadhara Somayaji. Tinnitus among Medical students using personal sound system. *Bengal journal of otolaryngol and head neck surg* 2017; 25:1 April:27-33.
8. Dehankar S S, Gourkar S S. Impact on hearing due to prolonged Use of audio devices: A literature review. *cureus* 14(11):e31425
9. Naik K, Pai S. High frequency hearing loss in students used to ear phonemusic: A random-

- ized trial of 1,000 students. *Indian J Otol* 2014; 20:29-32.
10. Acharya JP, Acharya I, Waghrey D. A Study on Some of the Common Health Effects of Cellphones amongst College Students. *J Community Med Health Educ* 2013; 3:214.
 11. Niskar AS, Kieszak SM, Holmes AE, Esteban E, Rubin C, Brody DJ. Estimated prevalence of noise-induced hearing threshold shifts among children 6 to 19 years of age: the Third National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, 1988-1994, United States. *Pediatrics*. 2001; 108(1):40-3.
 12. Shargorodsky J, Curhan SG, Curhan GC, Eavey R. Change in prevalence of hearing loss in US adolescents. *JAMA*. 2010;304(7):772-8. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2010.1124>.
 13. Vogel I, Brug J, Hosli EJ, van der Ploeg CP, Raat H. MP3 players and hearing loss: adolescents' perceptions of loud music and hearing conservation. *J Pediatr*. 2008;152(3):400-4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2007.07.009>.
 14. Kim MG, Hong SM, Shim HJ, Kim YD, Cha CI, Yeo SG. Hearing threshold of Korean adolescents associated with the use of personal music players. *Yonsei Med J*. 2009;50(6):771-6.
 15. Kumar A, Mathew K, Alexander SA, Kiran C. Output sound pressure levels of personal music systems and their effect on hearing. *Noise Health*. 2009; 11(44): 132-140.
 16. Chung JH, Des Roches CM, Meunier J, Eavey RD. Evaluation of noise-induced hearing loss in young people using a web-based survey technique. *Pediatrics*. 2005;115(4):861-7.
 17. Ansari H, Mohammad poorasl A, Rostami F, Maleki A, Sahebighah MH, Naieni KH. Pattern of use of earphone and music player devices among Iranian adolescents. *Int J Prev Med*. 2014;5(6):776-81.
 18. Wandadi M, Rashedi V, Heidari A. Prevalence of using personal music player and listening habit in students. *J Rehabil Sci Res*. 2014;1(2):30-2.
 19. Katz J, Burkard RF, Medwetsky L. *Handbook of clinical audiology*. 5th ed. Philadelphia, PA: Lippincott, Williams and Wilkins; 2002. p. 125-30.
 20. Lee GJ, Lim MY, Kuan AY, Teo JH, Tan HG, Low WK. The music listening preferences and habits of youths in Singapore and its relation to leisure noise-induced hearing loss. *Singapore Med J*. 2014;55(2):72-7.
 21. Sulaiman AH, Seluakumaran K, Husain R. Hearing risk associated with the usage of personal listening devices among urban high school students in Malaysia. *Public Health*. 2013;127(8):710-5.
 22. Vogel I, Verschuure H, van der Ploeg CP, Brug J, Raat H. Adolescents and MP3 players: too many risks, too few precautions. *Pediatrics*. 2009;123(6): 953-8.
 23. Gilles A, Van Hal G, De Ridder D, Wouters K, Van de Heyning P. Epidemiology of noise-induced tinnitus and the attitudes and beliefs towards noise and hearing protection in adolescents. *PLoS One*. 2013;8(7).70297.
 24. Del Giacco AM, Serpanos YC. Education and knowledge of noise exposure, hearing loss, and hearing conservation in college students. *Contemp Issues Commun Sci Disord*. 2015; 42:88.
 25. Mahboubi H, Oliaei S, Kiumehr S, Dwabe S, Djalilian HR. The prevalence and characteristics of tinnitus in the youth population of the United States. *Laryngoscope*. 2013;123(8):2001-8. [PubMed ID: 23606449]. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lary.24015>.